

A Proof of the Reciprocal Sum Formula for all the Nontrivial Zeros

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ABSTRACT. The Reciprocal Sum (formula) for all of the nontrivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function is a constant, namely, $1/2 (2 + \gamma - \ln 4\pi)$ [1], and also a supernatural result. Based on some research findings since Riemann Hypothesis was proposed, our paper provides a proof of this formula.

1 Introduction

In his epoch-making paper "On the Number of Primes Less Than a Given Magnitude" [2], Bernhard Riemann proved, to date, the only analytic expression that reveals the essence of prime numbers, which is the prime counting function [3, p.34] – the number of primes less than any given magnitude, and proposed the renowned Riemann Hypothesis.

Throughout the mathematical derivation process of this paper, the reciprocal sum relationship (formula) of all nontrivial zeros as

$$(1) \quad \sum_{\text{all } \rho} \frac{1}{\rho} = \frac{2 + \gamma - \ln 4\pi}{2},$$

is not necessary, so it did not appear in his paper. Instead, it exists in the Riemann's nachlass [1] below that conceived his paper.

Figure 1. Riemann's numerical value of the reciprocal sum formula [1, p.72/168].

As shown in Figure 1 above, what is even more surprising is that by hand, that era, Riemann accurately calculated this value to 20 decimal places. This may have helped him in his computations of the first few nontrivial zeros [3, p.67] [4].

Even today, with the limited understanding of the nontrivial zeros in seemingly random distributions, upon reflection, we can fill its magic. This infinite reciprocal sum converges to a constant — a property that embodies the participation of all nontrivial zeros (as the content stated in Riemann Hypothesis). Therefore, this reciprocal sum formula (constant) naturally is fascinating.

2 The Proof of the Reciprocal Sum Formula (Constant)

The reciprocal sum [1, p.72/168] of all nontrivial zeros of the Riemann $\zeta(s)$ or $\xi(s)$ function can be expressed as

$$(2) \quad \sum_{\text{all } \rho} \frac{1}{\rho} = \frac{2 + \gamma - \ln 4\pi}{2} = \kappa_1.$$

We notate this as the Riemann reciprocal sum constant and κ_1 , separately.

Proof:

2.1 To verify $\zeta'(0)/\zeta(0) = \ln 2\pi$

We start with the first Riemann's functional equation of $\zeta(s)$

$$\zeta(s) = 2^s \pi^{s-1} \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \Gamma(1-s) \zeta(1-s).$$

Taking the logarithmic differentiation on both sides of the equation above yields

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\zeta'}{\zeta}(s) &= \ln 2 + \ln \pi + \frac{\pi \cos\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right)}{2 \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right)} - \frac{\Gamma'}{\Gamma}(1-s) - \frac{\zeta'}{\zeta}(1-s) \\ &= \ln 2\pi + \frac{\pi}{2} \cot\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) - \psi(1-s) - \frac{\zeta'}{\zeta}(1-s), \end{aligned}$$

where, $\psi(s) = \Gamma'(s)/\Gamma(s)$ is the Digamma function.

Below is an analysis of the asymptotic behavior of the last three terms in the above equation:

The Taylor expansion of $\cot(\pi s/2)$ is shown as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\pi}{2} \cot(x) \Big|_{x=\frac{\pi s}{2}} &= \frac{\pi}{2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n 2^{2n} B_{2n}}{(2n)!} x^{2n-1} \Big|_{x=\frac{\pi s}{2}}, \quad \text{for } |x| < \frac{\pi}{2} \\ &= \frac{\pi}{2} \left(\frac{1}{x} - \frac{x}{3} - \frac{x^3}{45} - \dots \right) \Big|_{x=\frac{\pi s}{2}} = \frac{\pi}{2} \left[\frac{2}{\pi s} - \frac{\pi s}{6} + O(s^3) \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{s} - \frac{\pi^2}{12} s + O(s^3), \end{aligned}$$

where, B_{2n} are the Bernoulli numbers;

The Taylor expansion of $\psi(x)$ in the neighborhood of $x = 1$ is written as

$$\begin{aligned}\psi(x)|_{x=1-s} &= -\gamma + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{n+1} \zeta(n+1) (x-1)^n \Big|_{x=1-s} \\ &= -\gamma + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{2n+1} \zeta(n+1) s^n = -\gamma - \zeta(2)s + O(s^2),\end{aligned}$$

so,

$$\psi(1-s) = -\gamma - \zeta(2)s + O(s^2),$$

where. $\zeta(2) = \pi^2/6$, in Euler's 1735 solution of the Basel Problem.

The Laurent series expansion of the Riemann zeta function near its pole is given by

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{s-1} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!} \gamma_k (s-1)^k = \frac{1}{s-1} + \gamma + O(s-1),$$

where γ_k are the Stieltjes constants and $\gamma_0 = \gamma$.

And so

$$\zeta'(s) = \frac{d}{ds} \left[\frac{1}{s-1} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{k!} \gamma_k (s-1)^k \right] = \frac{-1}{(s-1)^2} + \gamma_1 + O(s-1),$$

hence

$$\frac{\zeta'(s)}{\zeta(s)} = \frac{\frac{-1}{(s-1)^2} + \gamma_1 + O(s-1)}{\frac{1}{s-1} + \gamma + O(s-1)} = \frac{-1 - \gamma(s-1) + O[(s-1)^2]}{(s-1)},$$

also namely,

$$\frac{\zeta'(1-s)}{\zeta(1-s)} = \frac{1}{-s} [-1 - \gamma s + O(s^2)] = \frac{1}{s} [1 + \gamma s + O(s^2)].$$

So that,

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\zeta'}{\zeta}(s) \Big|_{s=0} &= \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \left[\ln 2 + \ln \pi + \frac{\pi}{2} \cot\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) - \frac{\Gamma'}{\Gamma}(1-s) - \frac{\zeta'}{\zeta}(1-s) \right] \\ &= \ln 2\pi + \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{s} - \frac{1}{s} \right) + (\gamma - \gamma) + \left[\zeta(2) - \frac{\pi^2}{12} \right] s + \frac{O(s^2)}{s} + O(s^2) \right\} \\ &= \ln 2\pi + \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \left[\zeta(2) - \frac{\pi^2}{12} \right] s + O(s) + O(s^2) \right\} = \ln 2\pi.\end{aligned}$$

2.2 To Confirm $\Gamma'(1)/\Gamma(1) = -\gamma$

By the product formula of the Gamma function,

$$\Gamma(s) = \frac{e^{-\gamma s}}{s} \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{s}{k} \right)^{-1} e^{\frac{s}{k}},$$

taking logarithmic differentiation on both sides of the above equation yields

$$\frac{\Gamma'(s)}{\Gamma(s)} = -\gamma - \frac{1}{s} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{k} - \frac{1}{k+s} \right) = -\gamma + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{k+1} - \frac{1}{k+s} \right).$$

So,

$$\frac{\Gamma'(1)}{\Gamma(1)} = \frac{\Gamma'(s)}{\Gamma(s)} \Big|_{s=1} = \lim_{s \rightarrow 1} \left[-\gamma + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{k+1} - \frac{1}{k+s} \right) \right] = -\gamma.$$

$$\mathbf{2.3 \quad To Prove} \quad \kappa_1 = \sum_{\text{all } \rho} \frac{1}{\rho} = \frac{2 + \gamma - \ln 4\pi}{2}$$

By the definition of the Riemann $\xi(s)$ function

$$\xi(s) = \frac{1}{2} s(s-1) \pi^{-\frac{s}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{s}{2}\right) \zeta(s),$$

taking logarithmic differentiation on both sides of the above equation yields

$$\frac{\xi'(s)}{\xi(s)} = \frac{1}{s-1} - \frac{1}{2} \ln \pi + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\Gamma'}{\Gamma}\left(\frac{s}{2} + 1\right) + \frac{\zeta'}{\zeta}(s).$$

By the Product formula of the Riemann $\xi(s)$ function,

$$\xi(s) = \xi(0) \prod_{\text{all } \rho} \left(1 - \frac{s}{\rho}\right),$$

taking logarithmic differentiation on both sides of the above equation yields

$$\frac{\xi'(s)}{\xi(s)} = - \sum_{\text{all } \rho} \frac{1}{\rho - s}.$$

Combining the two $\xi'(s)/\xi(s)$ equations above, and limiting them on both sides, gives us

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \sum_{\text{all } \rho} \frac{1}{\rho - s} = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \left[- \frac{\xi'(s)}{\xi(s)} \right] = \lim_{s \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{-1}{s-1} + \frac{1}{2} \ln \pi - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\Gamma'}{\Gamma}\left(\frac{s}{2} + 1\right) - \frac{\zeta'}{\zeta}(s) \right].$$

Therefore, we finally obtain

$$\kappa_1 = \sum_{\text{all } \rho} \frac{1}{\rho} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\rho_n} = \frac{-1}{0-1} + \frac{1}{2} \ln \pi - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\Gamma'}{\Gamma}\left(\frac{0}{2} + 1\right) - \frac{\zeta'}{\zeta}(0) = \frac{2 + \gamma - \ln 4\pi}{2}.$$

Regarding the absolute convergence of the Riemann reciprocal sum formula, $\kappa_1 = \sum 1/\rho$, it is better to refer to Edward's brilliant proof [3, p.42-43].

References

- [1]
- [2]
- [3]
- [4]

©. ZHOU,
 卐. ZHOU, ChDGTDQ

pdebox@yahoo.com
 pdebox@126.com